

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Avizienis, "The n-version approach to fault-tolerant software," *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, vol. SE-11, no. 12, 1985.
- [2] A. Avizienis, J. C. Laprie, B. Randell, and C. Landwehr, "Basic concepts and taxonomy of dependable and secure computing," *IEEE Transactions on Dependable and Secure Computing*, vol. 1, no. 1, 2004.
- [3] D. Beder and R. Araujo, "Towards the definition of a context-aware exception handling mechanism," in *5th Latin-American Symposium on Dependable Computing Workshops (LADC)*, 2011, pp. 25–28.
- [4] H. Cai, C. Peng, and Y. Zhang, "A novel framework of self-adaptive fault-tolerant for pervasive computing," in *6th International Conference on Innovative Mobile and Internet Services in Ubiquitous Computing (IMIS)*, 2012, pp. 286–291.
- [5] B. A. Capraru, "Robustness and scalability: A dual challenge for autonomic architectures," in *4th European Conference on Software Architecture: Companion Volume (ECSA)*, 2010, pp. 22–26.
- [6] C. Chen, C. Ye, and H. Jacobsen, "Hybrid context inconsistency resolution for context-aware services," in *27th International Conference on Pervasive Computing and Communications (PerCom)*, 2011, pp. 10–19.
- [7] N. J. Chen and P. Lin, "An adaptive fault-tolerant mechanism for web services based on context awareness," in *4th International Conference on Computer Science Education (ICCSE)*, 2009, pp. 898–903.
- [8] S. Cheng, D. Garlan, B. R. Schmerl, J. P. Sousa, B. Spitznagel, and P. Steenkiste, "Using architectural style as a basis for system self-repair," in *2th Working Conference on Software Architecture (WICSA)*, vol. 224, 2002, pp. 45–59.
- [9] E. Cho and S. Helal, "A situation-based exception detection mechanism for safety in pervasive systems," in *12th International Symposium on Applications and the Internet (SAINT)*, 2011, pp. 196–201.
- [10] —, "Toward efficient detection of semantic exceptions in context-aware systems," in *International Workshop on Embedded Intelligence and Smart Systems (WEISS)*, 2012, pp. 826–831.
- [11] D. Crestani, K. Godary-Dejean, and L. Lapierre, "Enhancing fault tolerance of autonomous mobile robots," *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, vol. 68, pp. 140–155, 2015.
- [12] J. Cubo, C. Canal, and E. Pimentel, "Model-based dependable composition of self-adaptive systems," *Informatika*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 51–62, 2011.
- [13] J. Cubo, N. Gamez, E. Pimentel, and L. Fuentes, "Reconfiguration of service failures in damasco using dynamic software product lines," in *11th International Conference on Services Computing (SCC)*, 2015, pp. 114–121.
- [14] Y. Cui, J. Lane, R. Voyles, and A. Krishnamoorthy, "A new fault tolerance method for field robotics through a self-adaptation architecture," in *12th International Symposium on Safety, Security, and Rescue Robotics (SSRR)*, 2014, pp. 1–6.
- [15] K. Damasceno, N. Cacho, A. Garcia, A. Romanovsky, and C. Lucena, "Context-aware exception handling in mobile agent systems: the MoCa case," in *5th International Workshop on Software Engineering for Large-scale Multi-agent Systems (SELMAS)*. ACM, 2006, pp. 37–44.
- [16] R. de Lemos, "Architectural reconfiguration using coordinated atomic actions," in *2th International Workshop on Self-Adaptation and Self-Managing Systems (SEAMS)*, 2006, pp. 44–50.
- [17] P. den Hamer and T. Skramstad, "Autonomic service-oriented architecture for resilient complex systems," in *30th Symposium on Reliable Distributed Systems Workshops (SRDS)*, 2011, pp. 62–66.
- [18] A. Ebnenasir, "Designing run-time fault-tolerance using dynamic updates," in *2th International Workshop on Software Engineering for Adaptive and Self-Managing Systems (SEAMS)*, 2007, pp. 15–15.
- [19] J. D. A. S. Eleuterio, F. N. Gaia, A. Bondavalli, P. Lollini, G. N. Rodrigues, and C. M. F. Rubira, "On the dependability for dynamic software product lines: A comparative systematic mapping study," in *42th Euromicro Conference on Software Engineering and Advanced Applications (SEAA)*, 2016, pp. 323–330.
- [20] C. Q. Filho, R. M. C. Andrade, L. S. Rocha, R. B. Braga, and C. T. d. Oliveira, "ContExT-U: a context-aware exception handling mechanism for task-based ubiquitous systems," in *28th International Conference on Advanced Information Networking and Applications Workshops (AINA)*, 2014, pp. 127–132.
- [21] R. Frei, R. McWilliam, B. Derrick, A. Purvis, A. Tiwari, and G. D. M. Serugendo, "Self-healing and self-repairing technologies," *International Journal of Advanced Manufacturing Tech.*, vol. 69, no. 5-8, 2013.
- [22] B. Garvin, M. Cohen, and M. Dwyer, "Failure avoidance in configurable systems through feature locality," in *Assurances for Self-Adaptive Systems: Principles, Models, and Techniques*. Springer, 2013, pp. 266–296.
- [23] I. Gerostathopoulos, D. Skoda, F. Plasil, T. Bures, and A. Knauss, "Tuning self-adaptation in cyber-physical systems through architectural homeostasis," *Journal of Systems and Software*, vol. 148, 2019.
- [24] A. Gorla, M. Pezzè, J. Wuttke, L. Mariani, and F. Pastore, "Achieving cost-effective software reliability through self-healing," *Computing and Informatics*, vol. 29, no. 1, pp. 93–115, 2010.
- [25] H. Haouas and J. Bourcier, "Dependability-driven runtime management of service oriented architectures," in *4th International Workshop on Principles of Engineering Service-Oriented Systems (PESOS)*, 2012, pp. 15–21.
- [26] M. Hofbaur, "Model based reasoning for fault-tolerant robot hardware and software," in *16th International Workshop on Robotics in Alpe Adria Danube Region (RAAD)*, 2007.
- [27] J. J. Horning, H. Lauer, P. Melliar-Smith, and B. Randell, "A program structure for error detection and recovery," in *Symposium on Operating Systems*, 1974.
- [28] P. Hu, J. Indulska, and R. Robinson, "An autonomic context management system for pervasive computing," in *6th International Conference on Pervasive Computing*

- and *Communications (PerCom)*, 2008, pp. 213–223.
- [29] R. N. Kashi and M. D’Souza, “Mitigating byzantine failures in multi-agent based dependable and adaptable avionics software,” in *3th International Conference on Electrical, Computer and Communication Technologies (ICECCT)*, 2019, pp. 1–9.
- [30] J. Kephart and D. Chess, “The vision of autonomic computing,” *IEEE Computer*, vol. 36, no. 1, 2003.
- [31] Y. Kim and E.-K. Kim, “Autonomic service reconfiguration in a ubiquitous computing environment,” in *4th Parallel and Distributed Processing and Applications (ISPA)*, 2006, pp. 584–593.
- [32] V. Klös, T. Göthel, and S. Glesner, “Comprehensible and dependable self-learning self-adaptive systems,” *Journal of Systems Architecture*, vol. 85-86, pp. 28 – 42, 2018.
- [33] D. Kulkarni and A. Tripathi, “Application-level recovery mechanisms for context-aware pervasive computing,” in *27th Symposium on Reliable Distributed Systems (SRDS)*, 2008, pp. 13–22.
- [34] —, “A framework for programming robust context-aware applications,” *IEEE Transactions on Software Engineering*, vol. 36, no. 2, pp. 184–197, 2010.
- [35] P. A. Lee and T. Anderson, *Fault tolerance: principles and practice*, 2nd ed. Springer-Verlag, 1990.
- [36] T. H. Lim, I. Bate, and J. Timmis, “A self-adaptive fault-tolerant systems for a dependable wireless sensor networks,” *Design Automation for Embedded Systems*, vol. 18, no. 3, pp. 223–250, 2014.
- [37] H. M. Lugo-Cordero, R. K. Guha, and E. I. Ortiz-Rivera, “An adaptive cognition system for smart grids with context awareness and fault tolerance,” *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 1246–1253, 2014.
- [38] E. T. McGee and J. D. McGregor, “Using dynamic adaptive systems in safety-critical domains,” in *11th International Symposium on Software Engineering for Adaptive and Self-Managing Systems (SEAMS)*, 2016.
- [39] K. Modukuri, S. Hariri, N. V. Chalfoun, and M. Yousif, “Autonomous middleware framework for sensor networks,” in *2th International Conference on Pervasive Services (ICPS)*, 2005, pp. 17–26.
- [40] R. R. Nair, H. Karki, A. Shukla, L. Behera, and M. Jamshidi, “Fault-tolerant formation control of non-holonomic robots using fast adaptive gain nonsingular terminal sliding mode control,” *IEEE Systems Journal*, vol. 13, no. 1, pp. 1006–1017, 2019.
- [41] P. Oreizy, M. M. Gorlick, R. N. Taylor, D. Heimbigner, G. Johnson, N. Medvidovic, A. Quilici, D. S. Rosenblum, and A. L. Wolf, “An architecture-based approach to self-adaptive software,” *IEEE Intelligent Systems*, vol. 14, no. 3, 1999.
- [42] L. L. Pullum, *Software Fault Tolerance Techniques and Implementation*. Artech House, Inc., 2001.
- [43] S. Ramakrishnan, “On self-adaptive process-based dependable web service composition,” in *Computation World: Future Computing, Service Computation, Cognitive, Adaptive, Content, Patterns (COMPUTATION-WORLD)*, 2009, pp. 173–179.
- [44] L. S. Rocha and R. M. C. Andrade, “Towards a formal model to reason about context-aware exception handling,” in *5th International Workshop on Exception Handling (WEH)*, 2012, pp. 27–33.
- [45] M. Salehie and L. Tahvildari, “Self-adaptive software: landscape and research challenges,” *ACM Transactions on Autonomous and Adaptive Systems*, vol. 4, 2009.
- [46] M. Sama, D. S. Rosenblum, Z. Wang, and S. Elbaum, “Model-based fault detection in context-aware adaptive applications,” in *16th International Symposium on Foundations of Software Engineering (ACM SIGSOFT)*, 2008, pp. 261–271.
- [47] B. R. Siqueira, F. C. Ferrari, K. E. Souza, V. V. Camargo, and R. de Lemos, “Testing of adaptive and context-aware systems: Approaches and challenges,” *Software Testing, Verification and Reliability*, vol. 31, no. 7, 2021.
- [48] M. Sliem, N. Salmi, and M. Ioualalen, “Towards reliability and performance prediction of autonomic systems with self-healing and protection,” in *4th International Conference on Cloud and Autonomic Computing (IC-CAC)*, 2014, pp. 35–43.
- [49] —, “Using performance modelling for self-healing and protection in autonomic multi-tier systems,” in *International Conference on Advanced Networking Distributed Systems and Applications (INDS)*, 2014, pp. 35–40.
- [50] G. Steinbauer, M. Mörth, and F. Wotawa, “Real-time diagnosis and repair of faults of robot control software,” in *RoboCup 2005: Robot Soccer World Cup IX*, 2006, pp. 13–23.
- [51] Y. Tohma, “Fault tolerance in autonomic computing environment,” in *Pacific Rim International Symposium on Dependable Computing*, 2002, pp. 3–6.
- [52] Y. Tohma, “Incorporating fault tolerance into an autonomic-computing environment,” *IEEE Distributed Systems Online*, vol. 5, no. 2, pp. 1–12, 2004.
- [53] M. Vargas-Santiago, L. Morales-Rosales, S. Pomares-Hernández, and K. Drira, “Autonomic web services enhanced by asynchronous checkpointing,” *IEEE Access*, vol. 6, pp. 5538–5547, 2018.
- [54] H. Wang, W. Chan, and T. Tse, “Improving the effectiveness of testing pervasive context diversity,” *ACM Transactions on Autonomous and Adaptive Systems*, vol. 9, no. 2, 2014.
- [55] R. Wieringa, N. Maiden, N. Mead, and C. Rolland, “Requirements engineering paper classification and evaluation criteria: a proposal and a discussion,” *Requirements Engineering*, vol. 11, no. 1, 2006.
- [56] C. Xu and S. C. Cheung, “Inconsistency detection and resolution for context-aware middleware support,” *SIGSOFT Software Engineering Notes*, vol. 30, no. 5, pp. 336–345, 2005.
- [57] C. Xu, W. Yang, X. Ma, C. Cao, and J. Lü, “Environment rematching: toward dependability improvement for self-adaptive applications,” in *27th International Conference on Automated Software Engineering (ASE)*, 2013, pp. 592–597.
- [58] T. Yoon, J. Choi, E. Cho, and S. Helal, “A formal modeling for exceptions in context-aware systems,” in *Proceedings of the 3rd IEEE International Workshop on Modeling and Verifying of Distributed Applications*, 2014, pp. 734–739.

- [59] M. Zaiter and S. Hacini, "Towards exploring context to insure fault tolerance in home automation medical system," in *5th International Congress on Information Science and Technology (CiSt)*, 2018, pp. 29–35.
- [60] P. Zhou, D. Zuo, K. Hou, Z. Zhang, J. Dong, J. Li, and H. Zhou, "A comprehensive technological survey on the dependable self-management CPS: from self-adaptive architecture to self-management strategies," *Sensors*, vol. 19, no. 5, 2019.
- [61] X. Zhou, Y. Jin, H. Zhang, S. Li, and X. Huang, "A map of threats to validity of systematic literature reviews in software engineering," in *23th Asia-Pacific Software Engineering Conference (APSEC)*, 2016, pp. 153–160.